

ISic0900

I.Sicily inscription 0900

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

wall

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacombs

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Βίκτωρν ἡγόρα

2. σεν τόπον ἄ

3. πὸ Ἄερίου

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492530

EDCS 39102057

PHI 140381

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0083 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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